

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. Nowadays, we can come across artificial intelligence in many areas of society. The influence of artificial intelligence is growing day by day. The usage of artificial intelligence is growing, including in the field of education sphere. Artificial Intelligence is a part of science that is created by human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems. The main objective of AI is to smoothen the interactions of humans with machines, as it is accessed by the smart system, human language processing, speech recognition, and machine vision.

The demand for AI is increasing globally. Whether it's real-estate or digital marketing, AI has revolutionized every sector and the education sector is not an exception. In fact, it plays a huge role when it comes to teaching and learning. At present, schools and colleges use artificial intelligence to improve their teaching methods and for better results. In this paper, we will explain the importance of artificial intelligence in education.

Key words: artificial intelligence, AI, the Internet, education, machine learning, educational data mining, algorithm.

Аннотация. В настоящее время мы можем встретить искусственный интеллект во многих сферах жизни общества. Влияние искусственного интеллекта растет день ото дня. Растет использование искусственного интеллекта, в том числе в сфере образования. Искусственный интеллект — это часть науки, созданная процессами человеческого интеллекта с помощью машин, особенно компьютерных систем. Основная цель ИИ — сгладить взаимодействие людей с машинами, поскольку к нему обращаются интеллектуальная система, обработка человеческого языка, распознавание речи и машинное зрение. Спрос на ИИ растет во всем мире. Будь то недвижимость или цифровой маркетинг, искусственный интеллект произвел революцию в каждом секторе, и сектор образования не является исключением. На самом деле, это играет огромную роль, когда дело доходит до преподавания и обучения. В настоящее время школы и колледжи используют искусственный интеллект для улучшения методов обучения и достижения лучших результатов. В этой статье мы объясним важность искусственного интеллекта в образовании.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, ИИ, интернет, образование, машинное обучение, интеллектуальный анализ образовательных данных, алгоритм.

Introduction

Prior to the introduction of computers and other related technologies, instructors and students, engaged in instructions and learning mechanically, or through the pure application of natural human effort. With the introduction of microcomputers, and by extension, personal computers in the 1970s, provided more computing power and marked an important transition to electronic computers for the mass market. In agreement, developments of the electronic

computers, more particularly, and the availability of the same for different entities across different sectors of the economy, was precipitated by the developments of personal computers in the 1970s [1]. Personal computers development made it possible for individuals and other non-governmental entities to own and use computers for different reasons. These transitions harbingered the proliferation of computers in different sectors of the economy and society.

Computer and information communication technologies have over the years continued to evolve, leading to the development of artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence (AI) is the ability of machines to adapt to new situations, deal with emerging situations, solve problems, answer questions, device plans, and perform various other functions that require some level of intelligence typically evident in human beings. In another definition, it is defined artificial intelligence as the study of intelligence behavior in human beings, animals, and machines and endeavoring to engineer such behavior into an artifact, such as computers and computer-related technologies. Drawing from these definitions, it is evident that artificial intelligence is the culmination of computers, computer-related technologies, machines, and information communication technology innovations and developments, giving computers the ability to perform near or human-like functions. In line with the adoption and use of new technologies in education, artificial intelligence has also been extensively leveraged in the education sector.

AI generally expressed by the general public as the ability of machines or computers to think and act as humans do, represents the efforts towards computerized systems to imitate the human mind and action. In this respect, the basic definition of artificial intelligence can be expressed as the skillful imitation of human behaviour or mind by tools or programs. It may be an illusion of the current structure to think that artificial intelligence will come within the computer format used at home. It could get into our lives within different functions and shapes. It claims artificial intelligence to be the new electricity of this age. Artificial intelligence is a candidate to be presented as the basic building block of the Fifth Industrial Revolution by providing itself to be a powerful factor in ensuring economic development with its potential. That could be why investments in artificial intelligence broke a record in China with \$40 billion in 2017. In line with its earnings from AI, China is expected to increase its gross domestic product (GDP) by 26% (\$7 trillion) by 2030. North America is expected to have a 14.5% increase (\$ 3.7 trillion) in the same timeframe. These data make the added value and global impact of artificial intelligence more understandable for the future economy, and in our case, for the future of education, which in turn, directs the economy and workforce, paving the way for the new Industrial Revolution [2]. The in-depth development of artificial intelligence will affect many situations, from the restructuring of the social order in the broadest sense to the education and administration processes in classes and schools. Schools that are expected to adapt to the digital age and embed 21st century skills in their main agendas are some of the main institutions that could be most affected by the development of artificial intelligence. It is pointed out that new forms of technology will fill in our lives and captivate our youth, and this case may leave schools with no choice but to make room for them. In this regard, how the stakeholders from law, business, education, and engineering perceive this development, and how they foresee artificial intelligence in regard to education form the focus of this study. Thus, the purpose of this study is to examine what the use of artificial intelligence in education means and what kind of implication it can reveal for the future of education, according to the opinions of the participants from different sectors.

Methods

We need a lot of techniques and technology to apply artificial intelligence for education. Such as programming (web development, mobile development, etc.), machine learning algorithms (Regression, classification, clustering), and the Internet.

As mentioned above we will overview in detail. Nowadays, we cannot imagine a lot of spheres without programming. Programming helps in order to realize applications that is created using AI.

Users are able to use AI application through applications (desktop applications, web applications, android applications, iOS applications). Next technique we will overview, machine learning algorithms.

In Educational Technology, Automation plays a vital role. It helps teachers define student success factors and their shortcomings. They adopt a customized learning strategy focused on information, adaptive teaching programs, predictive modelling using Machine learning and artificial intelligence, and track the quality of teaching during their curricula. Teacher data analysis helps them understand their students' learning strengths and weaknesses because it facilitates a deeply ingrained cultural process that relies on precise information as an input to produce optimal results (results for students). Artificial education, data processing and graduates are all incorporated into the Machine Learning framework to improve online training. AI will allow educational software to be customized for each student one day. Student-friendly adaptive learning software and games are already on the market. One of the most important AI applications in education is making learning more comfortable and removing personal information from the equation. Education 4.0, powered by intelligent sensors and fitness bands, improves learning insight by multifunctional knowledge that integrates learning experiences (online practices) with data sources (real-time data) [3].

It is described machine Learning (ML) as "an area of study that allows learners to process without even being pattern recognition.". Self-configuring applications, dataset mining, semantic Technology (recognizing, thinking, understanding, interacting), communicative channels, computer vision, speech recognition. The results of Technology in engineering education, similar to the investigator. Computer-supported cooperative work (CSCW) uses software and Technology to assist a group of people working on projects across multiple locations. It is based on group coordination and collaborative activities supported by computer systems. IT systems diagnostics, troubleshooting, maintenance, and repair are all part of computer support and services. Maintaining a computer system's overall functionality is a primary responsibility of computer systems administrators (CSOs). Smart stuff (the web-based technology and gadgets catalogue), Virtual Twin and Learning process (the virtual image of what goes on within the mind of the educators), Computational Innovations (the merging of simulated and physical worlds) to establish the integrated, new technological and linked setting. Algorithms in data mining (also known as machine learning) are sets of heuristics and calculations used to build a model from the data. Data is analyzed using these parameters to find patterns and statistics that can guide future research. Virtual instrumentation, which combines software customization with modular measurement hardware, can create user-defined measurement systems. Even virtual instruments, which emphasize modular hardware approaches, can achieve this level of measurement specificity.

We need one more techniques, it is the Internet. The above mentioned processes require a high internet speed. High-speed Internet helps[4] to use full advantage of applications that is created the based on AI.

Results

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are key drivers of growth and innovation in every industry, and this is no different in the education sector. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has made significant inroads into a wide range of industries since its early days of robots and voice-activated machines. Artificial intelligence has indeed served to amplify the toil of those who put in the hours. This allows educators to focus on developing engaging and challenging curricula while automating much of the back-end support work for them. AI tools have also helped to refocus attention on accessibility. According to the eLearning Industry, as many as 60% of learning management tools will be equipped with AI capabilities in the next five years. While AI-powered solutions have been around for some time, the education technology industry has been slow to adopt them." Teachers were forced to rely on technology for virtual learning because of the pandemic and when it comes to technology in education, 87% of educators agree to the extent that Artificial intelligence in education can be used to improve educational outcomes. As a starting point, let's take a look at how these tools are currently being used to support educational institutions' efforts to make learning more accessible. It's also critical to begin by asking the appropriate questions. What are some educational applications of artificial intelligence? What aspects of human cognition are being omitted in the development of machine learning algorithms? Is there a way to incorporate AI into educational workflows that is more convenient for students? There are many ways that AI can be used to improve education for both students and teachers [5].

Over the last few years, online education has become more and more commonplace. However, they aren't the only ones who benefit from technological aid. Anti-plagiarism programs like Grammarly, word tune, and Turnitin have been widely used by instructors for years. Professors don't want students to be caught plagiarizing each other's work. To counteract plagiarism, some new teaching technologies are being developed ahead of time. Let's take a step back and remember that everyone learns differently. Some students learn best through auditory means, and others learn best through reading. Most professors already use presentations and speaking, so readers are left out. Using a voice-to-text program, professors can turn their lectures into a transcript. Students are encouraged to read ahead of time and come prepared with questions, or they can follow along and take notes during the lecture and not just list the lecture verbatim. It's impossible to overstate how much technology has changed education. Artificial intelligence (AI) can assist in testing in a manner like plagiarism this can be done with the help of natural language processing (NLP). For even more time-saving benefits, you could instead simply insert the scanner into the scanner machine! Educators hope that artificial intelligence in the classroom will make their workdays more efficient while also providing students with timely feedback.

To put it another way, a student's goal is simple, get an academic credential. AI can make it easier for students to achieve their educational goals by speeding up the learning process. With the right courses, better teacher-student communication, and more time for other activities, AI can have a significant impact on students' educational journeys. Below are some benefits.

Personalization

One of the hottest topics in education right now is the idea of tailoring instruction to each student's unique needs. Students are now able to learn in a way that is tailored to their own unique experiences and preferences thanks to the use of AI. Artificial intelligence (AI) can adjust to the specific needs of each student, considering their current level of knowledge, learning rate, and desired to learn outcomes. Artificial intelligence (AI)-driven solutions can also analyze students' previous learning histories to identify weaknesses and recommend courses that are best suited for improvement, providing numerous opportunities for a personalized learning experience.

Coaching

Because of their busy schedules, many teachers can't accommodate students who need extra help after school-homeschooling or on weekends. In these cases, AI tutors and chatbots are the ideal solutions. Although Chatbots cannot replace teachers, AI tools can help students improve their weaknesses outside of the classroom. A one-on-one learning experience without the teacher is available at all hours of the day with the help of AI. Student questions can be answered in as little as 5 seconds by an AI-powered chatbot.

Prompt response

When you ask a question and get an answer three days later, it's frustrating. Daily, teachers and faculty members are bombarded with the same questions. Student questions can be answered in a matter of seconds using support automation and conversational intelligence provided by AI. This not only saves teachers a great deal of time but also makes it easier for students to find answers to their questions.

Constant Support

Students can learn at any time and from any location thanks to AI-powered tools. 24/7 access makes it easier for students to discover what works best for them without having to wait for an instructor's approval. As a result, students from all over the world can gain access to high-quality education without incurring travel or living expenses.

Time management is a problem for most teachers and faculty members, which is understandable given the number of tasks they have on their daily to-do lists. While teachers would like to spend additional time with students, conducting research, and furthering their education, they simply do not have the time to do so. By automating tasks, analyzing student performance, and closing the educational gap, AI can free up educators' time and help them better serve their students.

Personalization

In the same way that AI can personalize students' distance learning courses, it can do the same for teachers. Artificial Intelligence (AI) can help teachers identify the subjects and lessons that need to be revisited. Teachers can use this information to design the best educational program for each student. To keep students from falling behind, teachers and professors must analyze each student's specific needs and adjust their courses to address the most common knowledge gaps or challenge areas.

Task Automation

It is possible to automate mundane tasks such as grading papers and testing learning patterns by using AI's power of computation. Teachers spend 40% of their time planning lessons, grading tests, and doing administrative work, according to a Telegraph survey. Teachers, on the

other hand, can use support automation tools to automate manual processes, allowing them to devote more time to teaching core skills.

Response to Queries

AI-powered chatbots can answer a wide range of generic and repetitive questions students commonly ask without involving a faculty member because they have access to the entire school's knowledge database. Artificial intelligence frees up time for educators to work on other aspects of their jobs, such as lesson planning, curriculum development, and student engagement.

The language barrier is an aspect of accessibility that is frequently overlooked. Technology has made the world smaller and more interconnected than it ever was. If you don't speak the language, it's difficult to get your point across. Students often travel to other countries to gain access to more resources and research. Educators can provide subtitles or real-time captions to their students to aid in their understanding. As English content spreads around the world, so does the reverse. Pre-recorded content is another way that more people around the world are getting access to education. Everyone is not in the same time zone, so not everyone can listen in on a live lecture. In addition to providing transcripts, teachers now have the option of providing videos with subtitles for their asynchronous students. Reading and listening to a foreign language together helps you learn it more quickly.

Future of AI in the Educational Sector

When it comes to smartphones and other household appliances, voice-to-text has become a common feature. But what if we went further than just setting timers and ordering food? Using machine learning, speech to text (STT) solutions can be utilized. Technologies like natural language processing (NLP) and automatic voice recognition (ASR) can have a significant impact on the way students' study and do their research. ASR technology can automatically generate transcripts of any audio or video by transforming the spoken word to text. Summarization, theme extraction and tracking of student participation are all possible uses for NLP in the classroom. With technology in the educational sector, you can gain access to a wide range of information. Higher education teaches students to specialize and narrow their interests. AI can draw on a greater range of information when [6] machine learning is used to augment lectures. Adding value to education can be done seamlessly. Even when artificial intelligence is used in teaching, accuracy is crucial. Even with the help of machine intelligence, instructors are constantly striving to produce challenging and original information. Please ensure that the intended quality of this material is maintained. Using an STT supplier like Rev, you are guaranteed 99% correctness in your transcripts, captions, and subtitles.

Discussion

Applying AI in education gives us the following opportunities. The main difference between this platform and others is that the prediction and classification of students' knowledge is based on artificial intelligence. The platform can give the student following advantages:

- A student can study subjects on the platform in a convenient place and at the right time;
- A student is allowed to restudy the subjects on the platform;
- The platform concerns individually for each student;
- Each student's exam is assessed by a system that based on AI, it helps to determine accuracy a student's knowledge.

Using the platform in the following cases could be effective:

1. In the education system of poorest countries
2. Lack of teachers
3. Pandemic period

We will overview above mentioned each case in detail.

First case, due to economic problems, many countries in the world cannot spend enough money for education. Educational buildings, educational materials, tools for education, teachers' salaries are required high costs. The platform can help to solve problems in the cases that spend less money for education.

Second case, there may be a shortage of teachers in all regions of the country. This case is not related to money, as the first case. In this case, the shortage teachers can be replaced by the platform.

Third case, due to the coronavirus that emerged in Wuhan in 2019 and spread around the world to pandemic levels, students in many countries around the world have not been able to attend classes at school. As a result, the quality of education in schools has fallen. Using the platform is effective in each case mentioned above.

Conclusion

In this paper, we overviewed the role of artificial intelligence in education. We can conclude about the process as following: low cost, possibility of reusing educational material, the students can study subjects on the platform in a convenient place and at the right time, the students are allowed to restudy the subjects on the platform, this platform offers an individual approach to each student, a student's exam in the end of module or in the end of grade is assessed by the system that based on artificial intelligence.

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